

A novel coated wire magnesium(II) ion-selective electrode : Determination of magnesium in dolomite sample

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A new coated wire Mg^{II} ion-selective electrode has been developed using Mg^{II} oxinate as electroactive material. The characteristics of electrode and application have been explored for direct determination of magnesium in dolomite sample.

A large number of Ca^{II} ion-selective electrodes (ISE) have been developed because of their application in clinical measurements. Relatively very few Mg^{II} ISE have been reported. Grekovich *et al.*¹ reported Mg^{II} ISE based on magnesium phenanthroline modified with tetraphenyl borate in orthonitrophenyl lactate. Bis- β -diketones as ionophores have been used for Mg^{II} ISE fabrication². Davison and Harbinson³ reported a complex of magnesium with diphenylphenanthroline used for fabrication of electrode. Another electrode based on magnus complex of tetraphenyl borate has also been reported⁴. Badertscher *et al.*⁵ reported Mg^{II} ISE based on N,N',N'',N''' -tetramethyl-aspartamide. Sachs *et al.*⁶ reported their preliminary results with a new Mg^{II} sensitive ISE. Alcade *et al.*⁷ measured few Mg^{II} ions in human erythrocytes. All the above noted electrodes follow the traditional barrel configuration and require not only large sample size but also have to be kept in upright position for the measurement.

Freiser⁸ advocated the use of coated-wire ion-selective electrodes which only require 1-2 mm in diameter of electrode and can be used at any angle with low cost. Several coated wire ion-selective electrodes have been developed⁹, but there is no report on coated wire electrode for measurement of Mg^{II} ions.

Here, we report a coated wire ISE for Mg^{II} ions and its characteristics have been studied for the evaluation of its usefulness for the determination of Mg^{II} ions in solution. One of the important aspects of use of coated wire ISE is that, it not only needs a very small volume of sample but also provides a means for real time analysis. Further, the operating cost of such measurement is low and the equipment is handy.

Results and Discussion

The electrode system can be represented as :

Metal (conductor) wire	Ion-selective membrane (bead)	Sample solution	External reference electrode (SCE)
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After conditioning, the potentials for a series of standard solutions of $MgCl_2$ were measured. A linear response was observed down to 5×10^{-6} mol dm^{-3} . The slope was found to be 30 mV per decade change in magnesium concentration. Below 1×10^{-7} mol dm^{-3} , the response was non-linear, but a calibration curve could be utilized for determination of Mg^{II} ions down to 5×10^{-6} mol dm^{-3} . Even with continuous use of the electrode, the slope remained constant for upto 29 weeks, after which it decreased.

To evaluate the response time, the electrode was dipped into 10^{-2} mol dm^{-3} $MgCl_2$ solution, and the potential was noted at 5 s intervals. A constant steady potential reached within 15 s. Approximately 15 s were required for the potential to come within ± 1 mV to its final value. To study the pH dependence of the electrode potential, the pH of $MgCl_2$ solutions, 0.1 and 0.01 mol dm^{-1} was varied by the addition of HCl or NaOH solution. The potential remained unchanged in the pH range 3.0–9.0.

The selectivity coefficients ($k_{Mg,M}$) for six cations were determined by the mixed solution method¹⁰ and the electrode has been found to be selective in the presence of these metal ions. The selectivity coefficients for different cations are as follows : Ni^{II} 0.1, Cu^{II} 0.01, Zn^{II} 0.01, Ca^{II} 0.01, Pb^{II} 0.001, and Mn^{II} 0.001.

The results of direct estimation of Mg in dolomite sample are presented in Table 1.

Sl. no.	Weight of samples (g)	Standard value (g)	Observed value (g)
1.	0.5	0.0621	0.0610
2.	1.0	0.1242	0.1220
3.	1.5	0.1863	0.1840

Experimental

Oxine (8-hydroxyquinoline; B.D.H., 2 g) dissolved in ethanol was treated with a dilute solution of $MgCl_2$ (B.D.H.) to obtain magnesium(II) oxinate¹¹ which was washed with water and dried for 24 h at room temperature.

Preparation of the electrode : A solution of PVC (0.2 g) dissolved in tetrahydrofuran (7–8 cm³) was mixed with the above electroactive material forming a slurry. A coaxial copper cable was coated by dipping it several times in the slurry until a bead^{9,12} was formed at the tip. The cable along with the bead at its tip was used as Mg^{II} ISE which was dried in air for 48 h.

A Philips PR 9405 M pH meter with a second saturated calomel electrode (SCE; Elico) as reference electrode was used for electrode potential measurement.

Applications : The electrode was found to be useful as an indicator electrode for potentiometric titrations. It was then used to analyse dolomite sample (No. 9h, Bureau of analysed Samples, Cleveland, U.S.A.). The sample (0.5, 1.0 and 1.5 g) was treated with HCl, then evaporated to dryness and the residue was taken up in double-distilled water and filtered. The filtrate was treated with NH_4OH and Br_2 and filtered. The filtrate was then treated with ammonium oxalate to precipitate calcium as oxalate and fil-

tered. The remaining filtrate was evaporated and then taken up in double-distilled water to 100 ml. The measurements were made by Mg^{II} ISE. The amount of magnesium was calculated from the calibration curve.

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